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IN THE KING COUNTY SUPERIOR COURT
STATE OF WASHINGTON

STATE OF WASHINGTON,

Plaintiff,

vs.

ANTHONY WAYNE JONES,

Defendant.

No. 24-1-00375-1 SEA

PRELIMINARY RESPONSE TO
FIRST PETITION FOR
TERMINATION

ORAL ARGUMENT REQUESTED

I. RESPONSE

Defendant, Anthony Wayne Jones (“Defendant”), by and through his attorney of record, Francis G. Huguenin of Carson Law Group, PLLC, submits this Response to the State’s Petition for Termination. The Petition seeks to terminate based on Defendant’s “communications/behavior” after the State deliberately declined to rely on urinalysis grounds available at the time of exclusion. On this record, that choice

1 reflects impermissible retaliation against protected First and Sixth Amendment
2 advocacy.¹

3 For the reasons set forth below, and as a preliminary matter, the Court should
4 apply *Mt. Healthy City Sch. Dist. Bd. of Educ. v. Doyle*, 429 U.S. 274, 284–87 (1977)
5 burden-shifting framework and enter gatekeeping relief, to wit is as follows: before
6 any termination evidence is taken or any witness is sworn, require the State to prove
7 by a preponderance that it would have taken the same action on contemporaneously
8 documented, speech-neutral grounds, identified by date and record pin-cite, and bar
9 reliance on protected petitioning relabeled as “behavior.”
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11 If the State cannot make that paper proffer, the Petition should be resolved
12 without an Evidentiary Hearing.
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14 II. STATEMENT OF RELEVANT FACTS

15 1. Institutional Knowledge of Testing Deficiencies

16 January 24, 2025: Treatment Coordinator Lizzy Deschane emailed DDCCS Case
17 Managers, “We have some new Xylazine positives. I am going to send a request to
18 Cordant to run confirmation testing on them for cocaine, meth, fentanyl and PCP.
19 With that said, we should not wait on the additional testing before addressing the
20 positives with the court and participant – I think when we do that it gives the
21

22 ¹ Scope of Response: This Response’s Constitutional analysis represents one of multiple independent grounds for
23 denial of the Petition for Termination. Defendant expressly reserves all rights to raise additional constitutional,
24 statutory, and contractual defenses. This Response does not constitute a waiver of any defense or limit
25 Defendant’s right to file additional Motions challenging this proceeding on any available grounds. It should also
26 be noted that the Court itself in the June 26, 2025 Status Hearing made clear that a Response is elective on the
27 Defendant.

1 impression that we need more information before addressing the positive UA, which
2 isn't the case. I have also requested permission to test some of the prior xylazine
3 positive UAs for PCP..." *Subjoined Declaration of Anthony W. Jones*, ¶ 3 and Exhibit
4 1 herein.

6 **2. Timeline of Constitutional Advocacy: A Panoply of Approaches**

7 **A. Scientific Approach**

8 On February 5, 2025 Defendant emailed then Case Manager Shawna Mokler
9 a paper he authored entitled, "*Ensuring Accuracy in Xylazine Testing: A Review of*
10 *Scientific and Forensic Evidence*," and requested a moratorium on testing until
11 accuracy could be improved, specifically to avoid the harm caused by wrongful
12 sanctions. *Jones Decl. Strict Reply Re: State's Response to Motion for*
13 *Reconsideration*, ¶ 4 and Exhibit 1 therein. This paper spanned seven key issues: 1)
14 pharmacology and detection, 2) xylazine's presence in the drug supply, 3) laboratory
15 testing issues, 4) behavioral science and relapse patterns, 5) epidemiological and
16 regulatory context, 6) Cordant Health Solutions reliability, 7) Best Practices in
17 Forensic Toxicology. *Id.* Each item was hyperlinked to peer reviewed studies or
18 relevant state-sponsored content (i.e. DOH website publications). On June 20, 2025,
19 Expert Testimony vindicated every single point Defendant raised in scientific defense
20 throughout his advocacy communications. *Subj. Jones Decl.* ¶ 4-5 and Exhibit 2
21 herein.
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1 **B. Advocacy Approach**

2 Defendant memorialized his advocacy intention in a March 10, 2025 email to
3 the Prosecuting Attorney’s Office. “I believe there will be participants who are
4 emotionally incapable of handling their honest efforts being invalidated in court, and
5 through relapse as a result, will die. Forever. If I don’t do what I can, I will feel
6 complicit. Forever.” *Jones Decl. Strict Reply Re: State’s Response to Motion for*
7 *Reconsideration*, ¶ 5 and Exhibit 2 therein.

9 **C. Philosophical and Moral Approach**

10 On March 27-28, 2025, Defendant submitted philosophical analysis to his then
11 Case Manager, Shawna Mokler. "What we see when applying Blackstone's ratio is
12 atrocious. The science presented...points to a grim inversion of justice—where no
13 guilty are walking free, and all innocent are being punished." *Subj. Jones Decl.*, ¶ 8-
14 9 and Exhibit 4 herein.

15 Subsequently, on March 28, 2025, in an email to Mokler, "harm doesn't come
16 from intention. It comes from momentum. From a room full of people each thinking
17 someone else is in charge of the ethics." *Subj. Jones Decl.* ¶ 10-11 and Exhibit 5
18 herein. Defendant concluded, "sometimes, the kindest thing anyone can do is say:
19 "This doesn't feel right. I won't continue. Let's stop the experiment." *Id.* The
20 experiment was stopped on July 1, 2025 when Drug Court was forced to reverse the
21 standalone xylazine sanctions. *Amended Motion for Mandatory Causation Analysis,*
22 *Subjoined Declaration of Francis G. Huguenin*, ¶ 4-5 and Exhibits 2-3 therein.

1 **D. Logical Approaches**

2 On April 2, 2025, Defendant submitted analysis regarding the Program's use
3 of "vape-sharing" explanations following standalone positive xylazine test results.
4 Defendant explained, "GC-MS confirmatory testing detects metabolites at nanogram-
5 per-milliliter levels," and stated that no published data supported passive exposure
6 detection at these levels. *Subj. Jones Decl.*, ¶ 6-7 and Exhibit 3 herein. Defendant
7 characterized this practice as an "Epistemic Brady Violation," stating that when the
8 State, "deploys a scientifically unsupported narrative to explain a test result it cannot
9 defend...it withholds...the very framework needed to contest the accusation." *Id.*
10 Defendant requested that the Program provide scientific data supporting passive
11 exposure detection at GC-MS thresholds or, in the alternative, to discontinue the
12 practice. *Id.* The Program did not provide such data in response to Defendant's
13 request.
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16 Then again, on April 28, 2025, Defendant submitted "*The Smoking Gun: A*
17 *Logical and Dialectical Analysis of State Response to Xylazine False Positives.*". *Subj.*
18 *Jones Decl.* ¶ 12-13 and Exhibits 6-7 herein. Defendant noted the program sanctioned
19 xylazine exposure without clinical intervention, while simultaneously relying on
20 contradictory forensic and clinical assessments. *Id.*
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1 **3. State’s Decision To Forgo UA Grounds And Proceed On Speech-Based Grounds**

2 Despite possessing three positive urinalysis results that were considered valid
3 grounds for adverse action at the time, the State avoided relying on these results
4 when excluding Defendant on May 15, 2025, proactively amputating strong speech-
5 neutral grounds for Exclusion and later Termination. Specifically, the State asserted
6 they were, “asking to set for a hearing and place on excluded because...Mr. Jones has
7 made himself needs exceeds as a result of his approach and his posturing...” (5/15/25
8 Hr’g Tr. at 4:03:17) *Subj. Jones Decl.*, ¶ 14 and Exhibit 8 herein.

9 **4. Prima Facie Showing of Speech-Based Motivation Requiring *Mt. Healthy***
10 **Analysis**

11 The State’s Petition contains numerous examples:

12 A. “From [her] perspective, it is not the positive UA itself or any other
13 potential non-compliance issues that make Defendant untenable to case manage...”
14 *Declaration of Christina Mason Re: Petition for Termination, Page 14, Line 10-11.*

15 B. On April 15, 2025, in Defendant’s Status Hearing, Judge McHale stated,
16 “...Tony's in compliance with treatment; his sober supports and healthy social
17 activities have been verified; his UAs are negative. Treatment reports that Tony
18 attended all treatment activities as scheduled and is a strong participant in the
19 Program.” Later in the same hearing, the Prosecutor stated, “...the State is putting
20 Tony on notice that the continued filing of [what the State characterized as] frivolous
21 motions...may result in the state ultimately seeking termination from the drug court
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1 program...” *Motion for Pre-Termination Clarification of Legal Authority and*
2 *Framework to Ensure Procedural Fairness, Subj. Decl. of Anthony Jones*, ¶ 3 and
3 Exhibit 1 Therein.

4 C. “Following receipt of the email, Ms. Mason asserted she was no longer
5 able to provide Case Management services for Defendant.” *Petition for Termination*,
6 p. 7, l. 16-19.

7 D. “Defendant communications has [sic] made it untenable for case
8 managers to work with him...” *Id.* at p. 11, l. 22-23.

9 E. “Defendant has engaged in adversarial behavior and communications,
10 eschewing the collaborative nature of adult drug courts. As such, the State is
11 requesting that the Court find by a preponderance of the evidence that Defendant’s
12 needs exceed the ability of DDC to provide services, and that Defendant’s continued
13 participation in Drug Diversion Court is no longer productive or possible. We ask this
14 Court to terminate Defendant from the King County Drug Diversion Court.” *Id.*, p.
15 13, l. 10-15.

16 F. Between the State’s Petition for Termination and Ms. Mason’s
17 Declaration, the terms “threat/ threatening” appear twenty-five (25) times in total;
18 neither filing quotes **any** statement by Defendant expressing true threats. All
19 communications at issue are emails; no in-person confrontations are alleged.
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III. ISSUE PRESENTED

1. Whether Defendant has made a prima facie showing that his protected activity was a substantial or motivating factor in the State’s adverse action, thereby triggering the *Mt. Healthy* burden-shifting framework and requiring the State to plead and then prove by a preponderance that it would have sought Termination on specific, non-speech grounds even in the absence of that protected activity.

IV. EVIDENCE RELIED UPON

9 Defendant relies upon the files and records in this matter, as well as the Subjoined Declaration of Anthony Wayne Jones and Exhibits attached hereto.

V. LEGAL ANALYSIS

12 Under *Mt. Healthy*, once a party makes a prima facie showing that protected activity was a “substantial” or motivating factor in the government’s adverse action, the burden shifts to the government to prove by a preponderance of the evidence that it would have reached the same decision even in the absence of the protected conduct. *Mt. Healthy City Sch. Dist. Bd. of Educ. v. Doyle*, 429 U.S. 274, 284–87 (1977). Washington courts apply this *Mt. Healthy* causation framework in First Amendment retaliation cases and pair it with the *Pickering* analysis for whether the speech is protected. *Pickering v. Bd. of Educ. of Twp. High Sch. Dist. 205, Will Cnty.*, 391 U.S.

1 563, 568 (1968) (citizen speech on a matter of public concern, balanced against the
2 government’s operational interests).²

3 Courts in other jurisdictions readily apply *Mt. Healthy’s* burden-shifting
4 framework beyond public employment to government decisions revoking
5 participation in programs or comparable benefits.³ For example, in *Friedl v. City of*
6 *New York*,⁴ the Second Circuit held that revoking a prisoner’s work-release shortly
7 after he pursued and appealed public benefits implicated constitutionally and
8 statutorily protected activity and stated § 1983 retaliation claim, an application
9 consistent with *Mt. Healthy’s* causation model. As another example, the Fourth
10 Circuit has expressly confirmed⁵ that *Mt. Healthy* “provides the appropriate
11 framework” for First Amendment retaliation claims in the corrections context,
12 reversing where the court failed to honor the government’s same-decision burden.
13 Accordingly, in that jurisdiction, once the defendant shows protected petitioning was
14 a substantial or motivating factor in the adverse action, the burden shifts to the State
15 to prove by a preponderance that it would have taken the same action absent that
16 activity.
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20 ² See *Sprague v. Spokane Valley Fire Dep’t*, 189 Wn.2d 858, 409 P.3d 160 (2018) (adopting *Mt. Healthy* “same-
21 decision” step and applying *Pickering*); *White v. State*, 131 Wn.2d 1, 929 P.2d 396 (1997) (articulating
22 Washington’s *Pickering* balancing).

23 ³ It does not appear Washington courts have substantively addressed this issue, making it a matter of first
24 impression.

25 ⁴ See *Friedl v. City of New York*, 210 F.3d 79, 87–90 (2d Cir. 2000) (recognizing § 1983 retaliation where
26 officials revoked work-release after inmate exercised statutory and First Amendment petitioning rights; ties
27 doctrine to *Mt. Healthy*).

28 ⁵ See *Martin v. Duffy*, 977 F.3d 294, 300–04 (4th Cir. 2020) (*Mt. Healthy* is the appropriate framework for
inmate First Amendment retaliation; reversing summary judgment where court credited official’s rationale
rather than applying same-decision burden).

1 The *Mt. Healthy* logic already animates the analysis in *State v. Starkgraf*, 29 Wn.
2 App. 2d 30, 539 P.3d 855 (2023), *review denied*, 2 Wn.3d 1032 (2024): the court
3 affirmed termination and declined to reach the First Amendment because the
4 decision was “amply supported” by findings unrelated to the defendant’s speech. That
5 mirrors *Mt. Healthy’s* same-decision step: if speech-neutral grounds independently
6 carry the outcome, no constitutional ruling is needed; if they don’t, it is. Accordingly,
7 *Mt. Healthy* burden-shifting fits Drug Court Terminations. References to “threats”
8 must be limited to true threats: “serious expression[s] of an intent to commit an act
9 of unlawful violence,” and warnings of litigation or administrative complaints are
10 protected petitioning. *Virginia v. Black*, 538 U.S. 343, 359 (2003); *Counterman v.*
11 *Colorado*, 600 U.S. 66, 74–81 (2023) (requiring at least recklessness as to the
12 threatening nature of the speech); *State v. Kilburn*, 151 Wn.2d 36, 43–46, 84 P.3d
13 1215 (2004).

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16 The Sixth Amendment and Article I, § 22 of the Washington Constitution
17 guarantee a defendant’s right to self-representation and a meaningful opportunity to
18 present a defense.⁶ Where adverse action targets advocacy undertaken while
19 exercising that right, courts must apply the *Mt. Healthy/Pickering* framework with
20 **particular rigor** to avoid penalizing the form of lawful *pro se* advocacy, rather than
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23 ⁶ See *Faretta v. California*, 422 U.S. 806, 819–21, 834–36 (1975); *McKaskle v. Wiggins*, 465 U.S. 168, 174–79
24 (1984); *Herring v. New York*, 422 U.S. 853, 858–65 (1975); *State v. Madsen*, 168 Wn.2d 496, 503, 229 P.3d 714
(2010); *State v. Rafay*, 167 Wn.2d 644, 652, 222 P.3d 86 (2009); *State v. Silva*, 108 Wn. App. 536, 539, 617–25,
31 P.3d 729 (2001).

1 its lawfulness. Put differently, the State cannot make the permissibility of advocacy
2 turn on who speaks: if counsel's making the same arguments would not warrant
3 termination or sanction of a defendant, then the defendant's making them *pro se*
4 cannot either.

5
6 Drug Court participation cannot be conditioned on waiving First Amendment
7 petitioning rights. Any contract term prohibiting or chilling constitutional advocacy
8 violates the unconstitutional conditions doctrine and is void *ab initio*. *Perry v.*
9 *Sindermann*, 408 U.S. 593 (1972). By extension, the State cannot terminate based on
10 'breach' of constitutionally void provisions.

11 Applying this framework to Defendant's matter, it appears that the State's
12 Petition for Termination, in its current form, is flawed – perhaps fatally.

13 14 **1. Protected Conduct Triggering the *Mt. Healthy Burden***

15 The First Amendment to the U.S. Constitution and Article I, § 5 of the
16 Washington Constitution prohibit the government from punishing an individual for
17 exercising the right to petition for redress of grievances. This protection applies with
18 full force in judicial proceedings: a court cannot penalize a litigant for raising good-
19 faith legal arguments, filing motions, or otherwise invoking legal processes to address
20 perceived wrongs. Defendant's activities at issue here – including filing motions
21 challenging Drug Court procedures, lodging complaints with oversight agencies, and
22 even drafting a § 1983 lawsuit – are classic petitioning activities. **They are**
23 **constitutionally protected.** The State does not (and cannot) contend that Defendant's
24

1 speech was obscene, threatening physical harm, or otherwise unprotected. To the
2 contrary, the content of his advocacy was legal in nature: he questioned testing
3 reliability, sought policy clarifications, and reported what he believed to be unlawful
4 practices. Such speech lies at the core of free speech protections, especially when it
5 concerns the integrity of this Court’s proceedings and the reliability of the testing
6 methods on which liberty turns.
7

8 While Defendant’s written advocacy was at times firm, it remained within the
9 bounds of lawful, *pro se* petitioning and case-related critique. The State cites *how* he
10 spoke rather than any rule he broke; that is not a neutral programmatic ground.
11 Under *Mt. Healthy*, disciplining a participant because of protected advocacy, however
12 unwelcome its tenor, triggers burden shifting; the question is content and causation,
13 not whether the speech was agreeable. The State’s “threat” characterizations identify
14 no statement that qualifies as an unprotected true threat. Without that showing, the
15 speech remains protected petitioning, and the State must carry *Mt. Healthy*’s same-
16 decision burden on speech-neutral grounds, including its Petition for Termination.
17

18 Applying *Pickering*, Defendant’s speech addressed matters of public concern:
19 accuracy of xylazine testing, program integrity, and adherence to governing law. The
20 State identifies no operational disruption beyond staff discomfort with Defendant’s
21 complaints, drafts, and filings. In a therapeutic court, a preference for “collaboration”
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1 cannot outweigh core petitioning and self-representation rights. On this record, the
2 *Pickering* balance favors protection of Defendant’s speech.

3
4 Further straining the State’s position, the “problematic” communications
5 occurred while Defendant was *pro se*. *Faretta* guarantees that a self-represented
6 defendant may advance the same arguments and defenses counsel could advance.
7 Under *Mt. Healthy* and *Faretta*, the State must plead and then demonstrate by a
8 preponderance of evidence that it would have taken the same action if those same
9 words and filings had come from counsel. Absent that showing, Termination on this
10 basis is impermissible.

11 **2. Cutting Off Its Nose To Spite Its Case**

12
13 The State is adamant that it is not seeking Termination for standalone
14 xylazine-positive UAs. Notably, in early May, 2025, approximately two months before
15 the July 1, 2025 policy change, the State stated on the record that positive UAs would
16 not be the basis for its Termination request. This begs the question: why not? By May,
17 2025, Defendant had three positive UAs that the State could have relied on. Yet it
18 voluntarily forwent the primary, straightforward, and speech-neutral ground that
19 drug courts typically rely on for termination grounds (a three-positive pattern) and
20 chose instead to proceed on “communications/behavior.” A neutral, evidence-based
21 administrator does not trade a facially “easy” UA path for a constitutionally fraught
22 speech theory unless the “easy” path is already known to be unsound. The sequence
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1 reinforces the need to apply *Mt. Healthy*: if any reliable non-speech ground existed,
2 the State would have chosen it.

3 **3. Inferences From Program Conduct: Uncertainty, Non-Escalation, And**
4 **Unresolved Conflict**

5 This section does not re-litigate toxicology, but rather emphasizes WHAT the
6 State knew, and HOW it acted. The pretext evidence is offered for two limited
7 purposes relevant to *Mt. Healthy*: (i) to show that, at the time the State pivoted to
8 speech-based grounds, its own conduct and communications reflect it did not treat
9 standalone xylazine results as a credible relapse predicate even while it was
10 sanctioning Defendant and others for those results; and (ii) to show Defendant's
11 protected petitioning about that defect was a substantial or motivating factor in the
12 State's decision to terminate him.
13

14 A. Sanction First, Search Later

15 In a January 24, 2025 email, DDCS Treatment Coordinator Lizzy Deschane
16 instructed Case Managers, while ordering additional testing, "do not wait" for
17 confirmations before "addressing the positives with the court and participant," adding
18 that waiting "gives the impression that we need more information...which isn't the
19 case." *Subj. Jones Decl.* ¶ 3 and Exhibit 1 herein.
20

21 At the same time, she (i) asked the lab to run confirmations across multiple
22 analytes (cocaine, methamphetamine, fentanyl, and PCP); (ii) sought permission to
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1 retest prior xylazine-positive samples for PCP; and (iii) acknowledged PCP is “out
2 there” but “not typically” tested absent a history. *Id.*

3 The same correspondence simultaneously recognized uncertainty and
4 potential confounders (by ordering confirmations and exploring PCP) yet directed
5 adverse action to proceed without resolving them (by telling staff not to wait and to
6 present the positives to the court anyway). That is not a neutral, evidence-led posture;
7 it is a sanction-first, search-later directive.

9 As a general matter, when a program imposes sanctions while the reliability
10 of the testing methodology remains unsettled, those sanctions are probative of pretext
11 rather than neutral enforcement. Program correspondence shows multiple batches
12 producing multiple standalone xylazine positives across multiple participants, each
13 followed by a sanction. That recurring sequence supports an inference of Program-
14 level pretext rather than neutral administration.

16 B. Sanction All, Treat None

17 In a therapeutic court, suspected relapse ordinarily prompts clinical escalation
18 (e.g., a higher level of care, or referral to residential treatment). During the period at
19 issue, however, Participants who returned standalone xylazine UAs, including
20 Defendant (three times), were uniformly sanctioned without any clinical escalation.⁷

22 ⁷ See *Subj. Jones Decl.* ¶ 16. On this record, no clinical escalation followed any of Defendant’s three xylazine-only
23 UAs; the State identifies none. Nor has Defendant, despite regular appearances at Status calendars and Program
24 meetings, observed any inpatient referral based solely on a standalone xylazine UA. If the State contends otherwise,
it must identify, by pseudonym, any instance in which KCDDC imposed inpatient or other liberty-restrictive clinical

1 That uniform non-escalation is a marked departure from ordinary practice and
2 indicates the program did not credit xylazine-only results as bona fide relapse
3 requiring a treatment change. If these were genuine relapses, one would expect the
4 program to employ its clinical tools, not sanctions alone.

5
6 Two features of the record reinforce that inference...

7 *Liberty Impact and Attrition Risk.* Residential referral is a substantial liberty
8 restriction that disrupts work, family, and graduation timelines. Imposing it on
9 Participants who had not clinically decompensated carried a foreseeable risk of
10 attrition (some were near graduation). The Program avoided that step, consistent
11 with the view that standalone xylazine results lacked a clinical predicate.

12 *External Clinical Verification Risk.* Referral to independent providers would
13 have triggered fresh assessments by relapse specialists. If those clinicians concluded
14 “no relapse: retest or re-evaluate the panel,” the program’s reliance on standalone
15 xylazine results would be immediately questioned. The decision to sanction without
16 referral had the effect of insulating the disputed results from outside clinical scrutiny,
17 again consistent with the view that treatment escalation was not clinically
18 warranted.
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24 escalation based solely on a standalone xylazine UA, with redacted support under Protective Order or *in camera*
25 review. In light of KCDDC’s July 1, 2025 vacatur of xylazine-based sanctions, any such instance would concede a
26 liberty restriction imposed on a predicate the Program has since disowned; if none exists, that absence corroborates
27 that xylazine-only results were not treated as bona fide relapse. The showing (or lack thereof) bears directly on step
28 2 of *Mt. Healthy*.

1 Taken together (i.e., uniform sanctions in lieu of clinical escalation, the
2 avoidance of referral, and the incentive to shield disputed results from external
3 review), there exists a strong inference of Program-level pretext rather than neutral,
4 patient-centered administration.

5
6 C. Exposure of a Record Level Evidentiary Conflict

7 Contemporaneous treatment reports from Therapeutic Health Services
8 documented no clinical relapse behavior for participants with standalone xylazine
9 UAs, including Defendant.⁸ In a therapeutic court, genuine relapse typically presents
10 with clinical or functional changes. The coexistence of a positive toxicology result and
11 the absence of clinical corroboration created a material inconsistency that the
12 Program was obligated to reconcile: either the laboratory result was unreliable, or
13 the clinical observations were incomplete. Proceeding to sanction while leaving that
14 inconsistency unresolved for many months undermines any claim that sanctions
15 rested on neutral, clinical grounds, and is consistent with program-level pretext.

16
17 On April 28, 2025, Defendant circulated a Memorandum mapping this binary
18 and proposing resolution steps (title as circulated: “*The Smoking Gun: A Logical and*
19 *Dialectical Analysis of State Response to Xylazine False Positives*”). Eight days later,
20 on May 6, 2025, the State first signaled that it would seek Termination.
21

22
23 ⁸ This inference is logical, not evidentiary: Defendant’s April 28, 2025 Memorandum identified the absence of THS
24 corroboration; on July 1, 2025 the Program paused xylazine testing and vacated xylazine-based sanctions. A claim
25 that THS nevertheless “corroborated relapse” on standalone xylazine results would be difficult to reconcile with the
26 Program’s own removal of standalone xylazine sanctions as a predicate.

1 The timing supports an inference of a pretextual shift from disputed neutral
2 grounds to adverse action. Defendant's protected petitioning was a substantial or
3 motivating factor in that decision.

4 D. The Sanctions That Never Were

5 While this record reflects sanctions that were available at the time of
6 Exclusion, those sanctions were later reversed, leaving Defendant with a compliance
7 record completely void of adjudicated sanctions.⁹ If speech (characterized as behavior)
8 occurred for months, and could form the basis for Termination, then a therapeutic
9 forum statutorily obligated to follow Best Practices would have employed graduated
10 sanctions before resorting to an extraordinary measure like Termination. Absent
11 such a factual record, the abrupt escalation to Termination also supports the
12 inference of motives probative of pretext, and *Mt. Healthy* analysis must follow as a
13 matter of law.
14

15 E. Temporal Proximity, Knowledge, and Admissions: Prima Facie Retaliation

16 Taken together, the record shows that protected petitioning was a substantial
17 or motivating factor in the State's Termination effort. By late April 2025, Defendant
18 had squarely raised the unreconciled toxicology/clinical conflict and proposed
19 resolution steps; Exclusion followed immediately. That proximity is coupled with (i)
20 the State's own admissions that the grounds were Defendant's
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24 ⁹ No sanctions have yet been imposed on Defendant for the missed meeting and UA.

1 “communications/behavior” (not relapse or rule violations), and (ii) a deviation from
2 therapeutic practice (sanction-only responses with no clinical escalation) despite
3 purported “positives.” On this showing, the inference is not coincidence but pretext:
4 speech, not neutral program criteria, drove the adverse action.
5

6 VI. CONCLUSION

7 Under *Mt. Healthy*, Defendant has amply satisfied his prima facie burden: the
8 State’s own admissions tying termination to “communications/behavior,” the
9 cumulative pretext indicators (i.e., abandoning speech-neutral grounds, shifting
10 rationales, and selective enforcement), and the tight temporal proximity establish
11 that protected petitioning was a substantial or motivating factor. The burden
12 therefore shifts to the State to prove, by a preponderance, that it would have taken
13 the same action absent Defendant’s protected advocacy. Having abandoned non-
14 speech grounds and hinged its position on speech, the State cannot credibly make
15 that showing on this record.
16

17 Therefore, Defendant respectfully requests that before any Termination
18 evidence is taken, the Court (i) require the State amend its Petition for Termination
19 to carry *Mt. Healthy’s* same-decision burden by proffering contemporaneously
20 documented, speech-neutral grounds with dates and record citations; and (ii) bar
21 reliance on protected petitioning relabeled as “behavior.”
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1 DATED this 19th day of August, 2025.

2 CARSON LAW GROUP, PLLC

3
4 */s/ Francis G. Huguenin*

5 _____
6 Francis G. Huguenin, WSBA #47098
7 Attorney for Defendant

8 I certify that this Memorandum contains 4,199 words, in compliance with the Local
9 Civil Rules.
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1 Deschane, Case Manager Shawna Mokler, Prosecuting Attorney Kristine
2 Schmidt, and Judge McHale’s chambers. I exported this message to PDF from
3 my Gmail Sent folder. The exhibit reflects the sender/recipient addresses,
4 subject line, and timestamp as they appear in my account. I have not altered
5 the content.

- 6
- 7 6. Exhibit 3 is offered to show the fact and timing of notice to the Program and
8 chambers and the content of my petitioning activity.
- 9 7. Attached hereto as Exhibit 4 is a true and correct copy of an email chain
10 consisting of (a) my message titled “A Heavy Heart,” sent on March 27, 2025
11 from ShweHollow <ahnahday@proton.me> to Case Manager Shawna Mokler
12 <smokler@kingcounty.gov>, and (b) Ms. Mokler’s March 27, 2025 reply (stating
13 she copied Christina Mason, Lizzy Deschane, and the prosecutors). On August
14 16, 2025, I forwarded Ms. Mokler’s reply to my Gmail account under the subject
15 “Fw: Re: A Heavy Heart,” and I exported that thread to PDF the same day. The
16 Exhibit reflects the sender/recipient addresses, subject lines, and timestamps
17 as rendered in my Gmail thread view; my original March 27 message appears
18 below Ms. Mokler’s reply in that view. I have not altered the content.

19 Exhibit 4 is offered to show notice and timing (that I raised these issues with
20 Case Management and who was copied) and the content of my petitioning
21 activity.

- 22
- 23 8. Attached hereto as Exhibit 5 is a true and correct copy of an email chain
24 consisting of: (a) my message titled “Some musings from this morning,” sent
25 on March 28, 2025 at 7:29 a.m. from ShweHollow <ahnahday@proton.me> to
26 Case Manager Shawna Mokler <smokler@kingcounty.gov>; and (b) Ms.
27 Mokler’s March 28, 2025 at 8:22 a.m. reply stating “Confirmed as received.”
28 On August 16, 2025, I forwarded Ms. Mokler’s reply (with my original message
below it) to my Gmail account under the subject “Fw: RE: Some musings from
this morning,” and I exported that thread to PDF the same day. The Exhibit
reflects the sender/recipient addresses, subject lines, and timestamps as they
appear in my Gmail thread view. I have not altered the content.
9. Exhibit 5 is offered to show the fact and timing of notice to case management
and the content of my petitioning communications.

10. Attached hereto as Exhibit 6 is a true and correct copy of an email I sent on
April 28, 2025 (subject: “Submission of ‘The Smoking Gun’ — Identifying
Structural Cognitive Dissonances in Court Practice”) from my email account

1 to the Prosecuting Attorney's Office: Drug Court Unit, Program Manager
2 Christina Mason, Shannon Blackman, Interim Managing Attorney KCDPD,
3 and Judge McHale's chambers. I exported this message to PDF from my Gmail
4 Sent folder on August 13, 2025. The exhibit reflects the sender/recipient fields,
subject line, and timestamp as they appear in my account. I have not altered
the content.

5 11. Attached hereto as Exhibit 7 is a true and correct copy of the document that
6 was attached to the email in Exhibit 6, titled "The Smoking Gun_ A Logical
7 and Dialectical Analysis of State Response to Xylazine False Positives." I
8 exported this attachment from the same Gmail thread on August 17, 2025. I
9 have not altered the content.

10 12. Attached hereto as Exhibit 8 is a true and correct copy of an excerpt from the
11 May 15, 2025 Drug Court Hearing Transcript reflecting the statement by
12 Prosecutor Kristine Schmidt at timestamp 4:03:17: *"...we're asking to set for a
13 hearing and place on excluded because, as we discussed during staffing, Mr.
14 Jones has made himself needs exceeds as a result of his approach and his
15 posturing..."*

16 13. I prepared this Exhibit 8 excerpt from the official Court recording for that
17 Hearing. I manually transcribed it myself. The excerpt accurately reflects the
18 words spoken at the stated time. I have not altered the content.

19 14. Neither of my two adjudicated xylazine-only sanctions resulted in any referral
20 to inpatient treatment or other clinical escalation.

21 15. From November, 2024, through May, 2025, I personally attended Drug Court
22 Status Calendars and Program Meetings. During that period, I did not observe
23 any participant referred to inpatient treatment based solely on a standalone
24 xylazine UA.

25 16. By contrast, during the same period I personally observed multiple
26 participants referred to inpatient treatment for UA positives for other
27 substances.

28 //

//

1 TO THE BEST OF MY KNOWLEDGE AND BELIEF, I DECLARE THE
2 FOREGOING IS TRUE AND CORRECT UNDER PENALTY OF PERJURY
3 OF THE LAWS OF THE STATE OF WASHINGTON.

4 DATED this 19th day of August, 2025.

5 */s/ Anthony Wayne Jones*

6 _____
7 Anthony Wayne Jones, Declarant
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Exhibit 1

From: DesChane, Lizzy
Sent: Friday, January 24, 2025 7:44 AM
To: Mokler, Shawna; Craft, Chris; Hayashi, Yuka
Subject: Additional testing on Xylazine UAs

Hi,

We have some new Xylazine positives. I am going to send a request to Cordant to run confirmation testing on them for cocaine, meth, fentanyl and PCP. With that said, we should not wait on the additional testing before addressing the positives with the court and participant – I think when we do that it gives the impression that we need more information before addressing the positive UA, which isn't the case.

I have also requested permission to test some of the prior xylazine positive UAs for PCP. Yuka received info from a new participant that they used what they thought was fentanyl and turns out it was xylazine and PCP. PCP is very much out there something we do not typically test for, unless someone reports a hx of PCP use.

Best,

Lizzy DesChane (she/her)

Treatment Coordinator

King County Drug Diversion Court

516 3rd Ave #E609, Seattle, WA 98104

☎ Direct: 206-477-0786 | ✉ lizzy.deschane@kingcounty.gov

Fax: 206-296-7885

Website: | www.kingcounty.gov/courts/clerk/drug-court.aspx

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Exhibit 2

Comparison of Expert Testimony on 6/16/25 and Mr. Jones' Writings submitted February-March 2025

1. **Philip Bost 6/16/25:** *"My understanding is that Xylazine is in the drug supply because it is an adulterant. It is extremely rare to see Xylazine alone."*

Anthony Jones (Exhibit A16) 2/5/25: *"Since xylazine is almost exclusively found as an adulterant in fentanyl, its rapid clearance compared to fentanyl's slower metabolism makes a standalone xylazine positive highly improbable."*

2. **Philip Bost 6/16/25:** *"People do not take it on its own, because it has undesirable mental and physical side effects."*

Anthony Jones (Retest Motion) 3/11/25: *"It does not produce euphoria or reinforce drug-seeking behavior."*

3. **Philip Bost 6/16/25:** *"These test results detecting only Xylazine are alarming because they appear to show a mismatch with the actual measurement of Xylazine circulating in the drug supply. There is not a proportional correlation of Xylazine only in the known drug supply."*

Anthony Jones (Exhibit A16) 2/5/25: *"Forensic data confirms xylazine is almost never found alone in the drug supply."*

4. **Dr. Kara Lynch, PhD 6/16/26:** *"Xylazine is an animal tranquilizer that is mixed with other drugs. It is not a drug that people seek out or use in isolation."*

Anthony Jones (Exhibit A16) 2/5/25: *"Unlike fentanyl or heroin, xylazine lacks euphoric effects, making it highly unlikely to spread virally within drug-using populations."*

5. **Dr. Kara Lynch, PhD 6/16/25:** *"The methods in our laboratory have never detected xylazine in the absence of fentanyl or norfentanyl in any urine specimens tested today. It is always found in fentanyl and/or norfentanyl positive samples likely due to it being a contaminate present in the fentanyl supply."*

Anthony Jones (Exhibit A16) 2/5/25: *“A positive test result for xylazine in the absence of fentanyl raises significant doubts about the test’s accuracy.”*

6. **Sophia Posnock 6/16/25:** *“Only after retesting by another lab that confirms Cordant’s results can a positive Xylazine test be part of the client’s drug court record.”*

Anthony Jones (Exhibit A16) 2/5/25: *“Adhering to best practices in forensic toxicology necessitates that initial positive drug test results be confirmed by an independent laboratory.”*

7. **Sophia Posnock 6/16/25:** *“The fact that Cordant has made no effort to check for error and has instead resisted complying with our subpoena for their lab testing methods casts doubt on their interest in ensuring accurate results.”*

Anthony Jones (Retest Motion) 3/11/25: *“Xylazine testing is an emerging forensic market, and Cordant benefits from expanding its use.”*

8. **Sophia Posnock 6/16/25:** *“This is likely due to their significant financial stake in contracting with this program, and calls into question not just the integrity of their test results, but their lab’s methods.”*

Anthony Jones (Retest Motion) 3/11/25: *“Further, granting this motion also **protects the Court itself**. If Drug Court’s unauthorized confirmatory testing is allowed to continue, it exposes the entire system to due process challenges, financial conflicts of interest claims, and potential liability for imposing sanctions based on procedurally invalid testing.”*

9. **Sophia Posnock 6/16/25:** *“Cordant’s deceptive practices have resulted in at least two high profile settlements in the last five years: one for deceptive billing, and the other for providing medically unnecessary testing.”*

Anthony Jones (Exhibit A16) 2/5/25: *“Lab reliability concerns—including Cordant Health Solutions’ legal history—raise significant doubts about the integrity of these results.”*

Anthony Jones (Retest Motion) 3/11/25: *“Drug Court’s reliance on a financially compromised laboratory raises serious due process concerns.”*

10. Sophia Posnock 6/16/25: *“It should be noted that Dr. Lynch, Dr. Sapienza, Dr. Ziegenhorn, Mr. Bost, and Ms. Oliphant-Wells all volunteered their time to analyze Cordant’s results and share their expertise. They declined expert funding payment for the significant work they have done. They are motivated by a concern is for the integrity and value of mass spectrometry testing and the harm to people in recovery that results from labs cutting corners and producing unreliable results.”*

Anthony Jones (email to PAO) 3/10/25: *“I believe there will be participants who are emotionally incapable of handling their honest efforts being invalidated in court, and through relapse as a result, will die. Forever. If I don’t do what I can, I will feel complicit. Forever.”*

Anthony Jones (Declaration) 6/13/25: *“And so I made a choice: that if speaking up could prevent even one unjust sanction, one relapse, one death, then it was worth the risk.”*

Exhibit 3

Anthony Jones <ahnahday@gmail.com>

Addressing 'vape-sharing'

Anthony Jones <ahnahday@gmail.com>

Wed, Apr 2, 2025 at 8:11 AM

To: Christina.Mason@kingcounty.gov, lizzy.deschane@kingcounty.gov, "Mokler, Shawna" <smokler@kingcounty.gov>, kschmidt@kingcounty.gov, McHale.Court@kingcounty.gov
Bcc: philipj@ths-wa.org, "Nicquelle P. Jones" <nicquellej@ths-wa.org>

Dear Drug Court,

I'm writing to address the program's continued use of the "vape-sharing" explanation following GC-MS positive results for substances such as xylazine or norfentanyl.

This narrative appears after sanctions have already been decided. It's presented as a possible behavioral cause—either in response to a participant's disbelief or as part of the program's inquiry. From what I have seen, one hundred percent of participants deny use (myself included twice), and one hundred percent (myself included twice) are asked the question: Have you been sharing vapes with anyone? The rhetorical shift onto the participant is unethical because the theory is scientifically indefensible.

GC-MS confirmatory testing detects metabolites at nanogram-per-milliliter levels. These results require systemic ingestion, hepatic metabolism, and renal excretion. No published data supports the idea that passive exposure via vape-sharing or incidental contact could plausibly result in detection at this scale. Environmental exposure—if it occurs at all—would produce presence in the body at picogram levels, which are several orders of magnitude below the GC-MS detection threshold. To put that in perspective: a picogram is a thousand times smaller than what GC-MS can detect.

Because the laboratory operates as a state agent for evidentiary purposes, the state assumes full constitutional responsibility for both the reliability of its results and the meaning of those results. Under *Kyles* and *Giglio*, the burden cannot be selectively applied: if the data is credible enough to sanction, it must be credible enough to interpret correctly. To claim otherwise is to weaponize uncertainty—sanctioning with one hand while disclaiming knowledge with the other.

Which leaves the state in a dilemma:

- If the program knows that passive exposure cannot cause a GC-MS positive, then offering vape-sharing as a post hoc explanation constitutes a deliberate misrepresentation—effectively assigning behavioral fault where none can be supported.
- If the program does not know, then the vape-sharing theory serves only to preserve the appearance of certainty—replacing scientific explanation with narrative control.

This is not a harmless narrative. It creates the illusion of explanation where there is only uncertainty. It deflects attention away from the limitations of the test and onto the participant, compelling them to adopt a theory that neither science nor the court can stand behind.

The result is a subtle form of gaslighting—offering a comforting fiction to fill the evidentiary gap, and treating it as resolution.

This practice also constitutes an Epistemic Brady Violation. When the state deploys a scientifically unsupported narrative to explain a test result it cannot defend—and presents that narrative to the participant as if it were evidentiary—it withholds not just exculpatory material, but the very framework needed to contest the accusation. The vape-sharing theory isn't information. It's a placeholder where real evidence should be. And by offering it in lieu of valid inquiry—even as a rhetorical question—the state forecloses the participant's ability to meaningfully challenge the result. That is Brady by another name: the suppression of epistemic clarity under the guise of explanation. This is a compelling example of the issues raised in *On Hybrid Jurisprudence*.

What's at stake here isn't just scientific accuracy—it's trust.

The universality of this question—asked not on the basis of evidence, but in every case where disbelief is expressed—reveals its function: not as explanation, but as control.

When participants are burdened by defending implausible behaviors to make sense of impossible outcomes, the system teaches them not that relapse is bad—but that truth is irrelevant.

If data exists to support the passive vape-sharing theory at GC-MS thresholds, I welcome review.

Otherwise, I urge the program to discontinue its use in all participant interactions and communications.

Sincerely,

Tony Jones

Pro Se Participant | Author, *On Hybrid Jurisprudence*

Exhibit 4

Anthony Jones <ahnahday@gmail.com>

Fw: Re: A Heavy Heart

1 message

ShweHollow <ahnahday@proton.me>
 To: "ahnahday@gmail.com" <ahnahday@gmail.com>

Sat, Aug 16, 2025 at 4:50 PM

Thanks and Best Regards,
 Tony Jones

Sent from Proton Mail Android

----- Original Message -----

On 3/27/25 10:51 AM, Mokler, Shawna <smokler@kingcounty.gov> wrote:

> Thank you for this email. I have included Christina, Lizzy and the prosecutors on my response as you are now pro se

>

> As you know, I cannot discuss other participants with you.

>

> Thank you,

>

> Shawna Mokler, MA, SUDP (she/her)

> Drug Court Treatment Case Manager

> King County Drug Diversion Court

> 516 3rd Ave # E-609, Seattle, WA 98104

> Direct: 206-477-5634 | smokler@kingcounty.gov

> Fax: 206-296-7885

> Website: www.kingcounty.gov/courts/clerk/drug-court.aspx

>

>

>

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>

> -----Original Message-----

> From: ShweHollow <ahnahday@proton.me>

> Sent: Thursday, March 27, 2025 9:43 AM

> To: Mokler, Shawna <smokler@kingcounty.gov>

> Subject: A Heavy Heart

>

> [EXTERNAL Email Notice!] External communication is important to us. Be cautious of phishing attempts. Do not click or open suspicious links or attachments.

>

> Shawna,

>

>

> I wanted to write you this morning to tell you my heart is heavy. I see Freddie and Lamonte grappling with their xylazine false positives, and I want to just let you know, each of these hurts all of us. Freddie is perhaps one of the best men I have ever met. My respect for his quiet humble moral fiber is without parallel. The man is doing good in the world and without boast or recognition. He lives for Christ, cuts people's hair for free because that's what he has to offer the world, and loves his neighbor like himself. I know, he knows, and the whole house knows he didn't do no xylazine. It hurts me to see such a good man wrongfully accused by what has every appearance of being pseudoscience. I guess we have to chalk it up to institutional inertia.

>

>

> And also Lamonte. When I email the prosecutor about the mortal danger of having honest efforts invalidated, this is exactly the type of person I mean. His false positive - before he even opted in - hurt him BAD. I am not saying he is relapsing, in fact he didn't and he isn't. He almost didn't opt in though. He was right before me that day with Judge North. The judge asked him to take some time to think about it, since he clearly was not sure he wanted to opt in, which is understandable considering. He sat down and someone else came up to be heard. I went and spoke with him, urging him to opt in. "You gotta opt in bro, trust me. This is a good program, you need this bro. We are gonna solve this dumb xylazine shit, I promise. Mchale said if we can show it is wrong he will reverse sanctions, I am almost there bro. Everything else in the program is amazing, they just gotta fix their testing, and we are doing it. Opt in bro, trust me, the program is good." He opted in. Ben, Cory, and myself have made sure to protect and guide him as he grapples with this, but we are all extremely worried about his well-being and his emotional capacity to deal with his honest efforts being invalidated. It's understandable. It hurts all of us to see.

>

>

> Five minutes later (I have attached the transcript. I bought the recording from the clerk's office and transcribed in Evernote, and manually verified it was accurate), the court eviscerated my 6th amendment rights. What is in the transcript is a confluence of structural errors that resulted in the complete deprivation of my 6th amendment rights. For full transparency, I also want to note that I filed formal complaints with both the Washington Commission on Judicial Conduct and the Washington State Bar Association on March 18, the day of the hearing. Each references the other. These filings were not made in anger, but out of a sincere belief that due process and constitutional integrity are responsibilities shared by all officers of the court. That process is now moving forward on its own terms. I mention it here only to preserve the timeline and ensure there is no misunderstanding as to what has been documented, when, and why. When the clerk emailed me the recordings, I submitted the transcript to both to supplement the complaints.

>

>

> I will not address these immediately, though there is enough there to reverse murder charges and worse, to be honest. I am still in this for the Freddie's and the Lamonte's and I won't stop until my brother's (and myself) get justice on the testing process.

>

>

> Today my heart hurts for my brothers. Seeing the xylazine on the UA receipt yesterday made me cry. I stayed alone in my room all day, even asked Ben to leave and give me some time. That receipt hurt me right where hope lives. I woke up this morning and realized it didn't mean we aren't winning, it's just institutional inertia. To be expected, until there is resolution in court.

>

>

> I also want to clarify something, since I get looks in the drug court office that make me very uncomfortable (never from you - honestly I am so lucky to have you as a case manager). I haven't done anything except document stuff. Hold up a mirror to the court, and spend time learning the law. Everything that has occurred is a result of the court's actions. It has a reckoning coming that will be difficult, but ultimately will preserve it for all future generations. This whole thing is still about returning to the core mission, which it has strayed from in its frothy rabid fixation on testing for unlikely target analytes like xylazine.

>

>

> William Blackstone famously said in his Commentaries on the Laws of England, "It is better that ten guilty persons escape than that one innocent suffer."

>

>

> Benjamin Franklin expanded Blackstone's Ratio, saying in a letter to Benjamin Vaughan, "That it is better 100 guilty Persons should escape than that one innocent Person should suffer..."

>

>

> Voltaire in his The Book of Fate agreed, noting: "It is better to risk saving a guilty man than to condemn an innocent one."

>

>

> With regard to the pseudoscience of xylazine testing, what we see when applying Blackstone's ratio is atrocious. The science presented in Exhibit A16 of the Supplemental Filing points to a grim inversion of justice—where no guilty are walking free, and all innocent are being punished. Xylazine as a target analyte in routine screening makes no scientific sense whatsoever for so many reasons. My own pain from personal experience grappling with my honest efforts being invalidated re-emerges sharper every time I see my brothers and sisters suffer similarly.

>

>

> I don't claim to know more than these men I have quoted, so I defer to letting them do the talking.

>

>

> My work on my motion is narrowing to proving a closed evidentiary loop inconsistent with the constitution of the United States. The Epistemic Brady Violation I authored is surprisingly real and accurate, despite being authored by a mind with a prison GED.

>

>

>

>

>

> Thanks and Best Regards,

> Tony Jones

>

> Sent from Proton Mail Android

>

Transcript 03_18_25.docx

11K

Exhibit 5

Anthony Jones <ahnahday@gmail.com>

Fw: RE: Some musings from this morning

1 message

ShweHollow <ahnahday@proton.me>
 To: "ahnahday@gmail.com" <ahnahday@gmail.com>

Sat, Aug 16, 2025 at 4:49 PM

Thanks and Best Regards,
 Tony Jones

Sent from Proton Mail Android

----- Original Message -----

On 3/28/25 8:22 AM, Mokler, Shawna <smokler@kingcounty.gov> wrote:

> Confirmed as received.
 >
 > Shawna Mokler, MA, SUDP (she/her)
 > Drug Court Treatment Case Manager
 > King County Drug Diversion Court
 > 516 3rd Ave # E-609, Seattle, WA 98104
 > Direct: 206-477-5634 | smokler@kingcounty.gov
 > Fax: 206-296-7885
 > Website: www.kingcounty.gov/courts/clerk/drug-court.aspx

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> -----Original Message-----

> From: ShweHollow <ahnahday@proton.me>
 > Sent: Friday, March 28, 2025 7:29 AM
 > To: Mokler, Shawna <smokler@kingcounty.gov>
 > Subject: Some musings from this morning

> [EXTERNAL Email Notice!] External communication is important to us. Be cautious of phishing attempts. Do not click or open suspicious links or attachments.

> Hi Shawna,

> This morning I found myself returning to the Milgram obedience studies—not just the facts of the experiment, but the weight of what they reveal about people, systems, and the quiet violence of expectation.

> In Milgram's setup, there were no villains. Just a man in a white coat, a participant, and someone in another room pretending to be in pain. The participant was told to administer electric shocks every time the person answered a question wrong. The voltage increased each time. The cries from the other room grew louder. Then they stopped. Silence.

> Still, the participants kept going. They weren't evil. They weren't cruel. They were conflicted. Sweating. Shaking. One said, "I don't want to do this anymore." But the man in the lab coat simply said, "The experiment requires that you continue." And so they did.

> The majority delivered what they believed to be fatal shocks.

> Stanley Milgram later wrote, "Ordinary people...can become agents in a terrible destructive process. Moreover, even

when the destructive effects of their work become clear...few people have the resources needed to resist authority.”

>

> The lesson was brutal: obedience is not a matter of belief—it’s a matter of perceived permission. People don’t need to agree to do harm. They just need to think it isn’t their place to stop it.

>

> And then there’s the Stanford Prison Experiment.

>

> Twenty-four college kids. Split in two. Half assigned the role of guards, half prisoners. No scripts. Just uniforms. Within 36 hours, the guards were stripping the prisoners naked, denying them food, waking them at random hours for pointless drills, taunting them, breaking them. The prisoners? They began to accept it. They internalized it. One had a breakdown. The study had to be stopped early.

>

> All of this unfolded without instruction. There were no evil masterminds, no mandates. Just roles. Just an environment. And people fell into them like gravity.

>

> Philip Zimbardo, the lead researcher, later reflected, “If you put good people in bad situations, the bad situations win. People are not born evil. But it’s astonishing how quickly they can become that way.”

>

> What I keep coming back to is this: nobody taught those kids to be cruel. The system did. The structure shaped the outcome. The silence around them said, this is normal.

>

> And I wonder—how many systems right now are running their own invisible experiments? No lab coats. No cameras. Just people, caught in roles they didn’t design, doing things they’d never imagine doing on their own, because the structure permits it. Because nobody else is saying no.

>

> Sometimes harm doesn’t come from intention. It comes from momentum. From a room full of people each thinking someone else is in charge of the ethics.

>

> And sometimes, I think, the kindest thing anyone can do is say: “This doesn’t feel right. I won’t continue. Let’s stop the experiment.”

>

> I keep thinking about the difference between responsibility and complicity. One asks you to act. The other lets you wait. Both wear the same face if no one speaks. And in some systems, all it takes to become complicit is to follow instructions exactly as written. Even if your heart breaks doing it.

>

> There’s something profoundly human about wanting to be part of something greater than ourselves. But I’ve also learned: the greater the system, the easier it is to disappear inside of it. And if we’re not careful, we trade our names for titles. We trade our voices for protocol. Until one day, someone is screaming in the next room, and we’re just sitting there, pressing buttons.

>

> Anyway. Just some thoughts, no need to respond.

>

>

> Thanks and Best Regards,

> Tony Jones

>

> Sent from Proton Mail Android

>

Exhibit 6

Anthony Jones <ahnahday@gmail.com>

Submission of "The Smoking Gun" — Identifying Structural Cognitive Dissonances in Court Practice

Anthony Jones <ahnahday@gmail.com>

Mon, Apr 28, 2025 at 3:22 PM

To: PAO Drug Court <paodrugcourt@kingcounty.gov>

Cc: "Court, McHale" <McHale.Court@kingcounty.gov>, "Mason, Christina" <Christina.Mason@kingcounty.gov>, "Blackman, Shannon" <sblackman@kingcounty.gov>

Bcc: Erica Barnett <erica@publicola.com>, Frank Huguenin <frankhuguenin80@gmail.com>

Dear Drug Court et al,

I am submitting the attached paper, *The Smoking Gun: A Logical and Dialectical Analysis of State Response to Xylazine False Positives*, for your review and formal record.

Unlike my previous submissions focused primarily on testing validity, this paper addresses two fundamental structural contradictions within Drug Court operations — contradictions that persist even if one assumes the laboratory testing is perfectly accurate.

Specifically:

1. Clinical Disengagement Despite Recognized Risk:

If xylazine exposure is serious enough to warrant sanctions, then under any therapeutically grounded model it must also be serious enough to require clinical escalation.

Sanctioning without treatment intervention fractures the court's rehabilitative mission, and exposes participants to unresolved — and potentially fatal — risks.

2. Unresolved Conflict Between Forensic and Clinical Findings:

Where Drug Court's own treatment providers and its forensic testing data produce mutually incompatible conclusions regarding participant behavior, continued reliance on both cannot logically or ethically stand.

If the testing is correct, treatment providers are systematically failing to detect widespread covert substance use.

If treatment providers are correct, the testing is systematically producing false positives.

Both cannot be true — and retaining both narratives month after month constitutes ongoing dereliction on at least one front.

As a pro se litigant, I am expressly submitting this analysis to be part of the formal administrative and constitutional record.

This submission is intended both to aid internal reflection and to ensure external accountability regarding the systemic risks identified.

I respectfully submit that until these contradictions are resolved, participant welfare, program legitimacy, and constitutional integrity will remain compromised.

Thank you for your attention to this submission.

Respectfully,

Tony Jones

Pro Se Litigant | Author, *On Hybrid Jurisprudence***The Smoking Gun_ A Logical and Dialectical Analysis of State Response to Xylazine False Positives.pdf**

96K

Exhibit 7

The Smoking Gun: A Logical and Dialectical Analysis of State Response to Xylazine False Positives

I. Introduction: State Duty to Truth and Consequences of Betrayal

The legitimacy of state power depends fundamentally on truthfulness in its representations. In *Banks v. Dretke* (2004), the Supreme Court held that when a state actor suppresses exculpatory evidence, it does more than merely act unfairly — it strikes at the heart of due process and undermines the integrity of judicial power itself. Justice Ginsburg, writing for the Court's 7–2 majority opinion, condemned the notion that "prosecutor may hide, defendant must seek," declaring it "not tenable in a system constitutionally bound to accord defendants due process."

The state cannot simultaneously claim the mantle of lawful authority while betraying the informational foundations that give that authority meaning.

This paper argues that King County Drug Diversion Court (KCDDC) replicates this betrayal in its treatment of xylazine urinalysis results. By operationalizing xylazine positives in a way that inflicts serious consequences without corresponding rehabilitative action, KCDDC demonstrates a profound cognitive dissonance that fractures its therapeutic claims and inflicts material and psychic harms on participants.

This betrayal is not hidden; it is operationalized openly, on the record, under the guise of judicial process — precisely the kind of institutional bad faith that *Banks* holds intolerable under constitutional due process.

II. Xylazine and the Demands of Therapeutic Justice

Xylazine, a powerful veterinary tranquilizer, has emerged as one of the most lethal contaminants in the modern illicit drug supply. Unlike opioids, xylazine overdoses cannot be reversed by naloxone (Narcan), rendering traditional overdose interventions ineffective. Its pharmacological effects — profound central nervous system depression, respiratory failure, and rapid unconsciousness — transform relapse from a clinical concern into an imminent threat to life.

Within any court operating under a therapeutic mandate, the appearance of xylazine in a participant's system should trigger an urgent clinical response. The risk of death demands it. In KCDDC's standard practice, confirmed instances of relapse — whether involving opioids, stimulants, or alcohol — mandate immediate escalation of care:

intensified treatment protocols, reassessment of therapeutic plans, and, in a significant proportion of cases, inpatient residential placement. Intervention in such cases is not discretionary; it is understood as operational necessity.

King County Drug Court claims to embody precisely this therapeutic philosophy. It professes a commitment to identifying relapse early, intervening aggressively, and preserving participant life through structured, rehabilitative measures. Within this framework, any indication of xylazine exposure — given its unique lethality — should constitute a red flag of the highest magnitude, demanding not only procedural acknowledgment but substantive, immediate therapeutic action.

Yet despite the known dangers, KCDDC's actual response to alleged xylazine detections remains **conspicuously muted**. Participants who test positive are subjected primarily to administrative consequences: phase resets, prolonged supervision, and minor sanctions such as written assignments or increased reporting requirements. No immediate clinical reassessment is triggered. No escalation of treatment occurs. The Court's operational response to xylazine — a substance more dangerous than the drugs it routinely escalates for — remains almost entirely administrative rather than therapeutic.

This disjunction is not merely an inconsistency; it is a profound betrayal of the Court's professed mission — a betrayal that, as later sections will show, cannot be explained by oversight or resource constraints, but must be understood as an operational decision rooted in institutional self-preservation.

III. Cognitive Dissonance: "Relapse" Without Rehabilitation

This creates a fundamental logical contradiction at the heart of the Court's response.

If the Court truly believes that these positive tests represent actual relapses into substance use — serious enough to warrant phase resets and other punitive consequences — then it must, consistent with its rehabilitative mandate, respond with clinical escalation. If, conversely, the Court does not believe that relapse has occurred, then **it has no legitimate basis to impose sanctions or resets at all.**

By resetting phases and sanctioning participants without escalating treatment, the Court reveals that it neither fully accepts nor fully rejects the significance of the xylazine positives. Instead, it uses the specter of relapse as a tool for procedural control — extending supervision, maintaining institutional authority — without incurring the burdens of genuine rehabilitative engagement.

This is not mere bureaucratic oversight, but a strategic performance of belief when belief is convenient, and denial when denial is convenient.

IV. Prioritizing Control Over Participant Welfare

KCDDC's conduct reveals not institutional confusion, but deliberate self-preservation. Phase resets are not therapeutic interventions; they are instruments for extending the Court's supervisory reach under the pretext of participant noncompliance. Sanctions do not serve clinical rehabilitation; they perform disciplinary theater, demonstrating institutional authority while avoiding the resource burdens and public accountability that genuine therapeutic engagement would demand.

Participants bear the full weight of this strategy. Progress is stalled arbitrarily. Standards of compliance become malleable instruments of control. Participants are punished as if guilty while being denied the status — and rights — of those genuinely in clinical crisis.

This is not bureaucratic inertia; it is operationalized self-interest. The Court does not weaponize relapse for domination; it shields itself from the unbearable consequences of self-correction. To acknowledge the instability of its forensic foundation would unravel not only individual cases, but the institutional narratives that sustain its legitimacy. Rather than confront the cascading collapse such acknowledgment would demand, the Court deflects, punishes, and extends supervision — not to dominate participants, but to protect itself from institutional self-immolation.

In this model, the goal is not recovery — it is the preservation of institutional credibility at the direct expense of participant liberty and welfare.

V. Weaponizing Epistemic Instability

The sustained contradictions in KCDDC's response do more than create bureaucratic confusion; they systematize existential instability for participants themselves.

Participants are trapped between irreconcilable mandates:

A punitive logic that treats suspected relapse as real enough to reset progress, and a therapeutic logic that refuses to acknowledge relapse when recognition would obligate institutional accountability.

This double-bind is not incidental.

It is operational: destabilizing trust, corroding morale, and transforming recovery into a

Kafkaesque gauntlet where hope is weaponized against the participant. Success becomes not the product of genuine healing, but of surviving an incoherent system that demands confession without belief and compliance without care. Rather than building the participant's capacity for genuine rehabilitation, KCDDC gaslights participants — making survival itself a test of loyalty to a broken epistemic order.

VI. Anatomy of Institutional Betrayal

The betrayal of participants in KCDDC is not the product of isolated error but of systemic failure across every institutional actor.

- The judiciary ratifies implausible forensic claims, extending supervisory authority while shielding itself from adversarial correction.
- The prosecution, armed with full knowledge of the system's evidentiary collapse, chooses not to confront it. Instead, it sustains the instability as a means of preserving institutional credibility — not because it believes the evidence is sound, but because acknowledging its failure would unravel the Court's entire narrative of therapeutic legitimacy.
- Defense counsel, entrusted with protecting participant rights, abdicates adversarial responsibility and becomes structurally entangled in the mechanisms of suppression.
- Case managers, tasked ostensibly with supporting participant progress, actively gaslight participants to shield epistemically unstable results from scrutiny — deflecting attention onto imagined infractions like vape sharing, and sustaining the improbable narrative that dozens of participants could repeatedly test positive for a substance with a thirty-minute half-life.
- Treatment providers, charged with clinical independence, refrain from contesting the contradictions between laboratory results and clinical observation.
- Even the testing laboratories, whose methodologies remain shielded from meaningful scrutiny, perpetuate the unreliable evidentiary foundation upon which the system's coercive actions are built.

Each actor, by action or acquiescence, sustains a procedurally incoherent system designed not to rehabilitate, but to insulate — weaponizing suffering as an instrument of institutional self-preservation.

VII. Conclusion: Collapse of Therapeutic Legitimacy

KCDDC's treatment of xylazine positives lays bare the collapse of its therapeutic legitimacy.

In its refusal to coherently resolve the meaning of relapse — believing enough to punish, disbelieving enough to avoid treating — the Court betrays not only individual participants but the very ideals of therapeutic jurisprudence.

Recovery, in this model, is no longer the goal.

Institutional self-preservation is.

And the price is paid in the shattered trust, stalled lives, and deepened wounds of those the system purports to heal.

Like the prosecutors in *Banks v. Dretke*, who undermined their own moral authority through strategic betrayal, King County Drug Court corrodes its therapeutic legitimacy with every phase reset unmoored from clinical reality. It punishes relapse without believing in it, and transforms therapeutic justice into an engine of arbitrary infractions.

Exhibit 8

3:42:13: Kristine: Anthony Jones Cause nber 24-1-000375-1 Seattle designation, Mr. Jones is present with his attorney today.

3:42:22: Frank: Ah yes good, excuse me, good afternoon your honor, Franics Huguenin here on behalf of Anthony Jones.

3:42:27: Mchale: Ok but you prefer to be called Frank, not Francis-

3:42:30: Frank: I do, kids were cruel.

3:42:31: Mchale: Ok. Yeah, that's, that's good. And so, Tony, how are you today?

3:42:37: Tony: I've been better, but I'm not, not too bad.

3:42:41: Mchale: And for you, what is the sober birthday?

3:42:43: Tony: I had a missed UA yesterday sir, so if that counts as a fail-

3:42:47: That's, that's different than the sober birthday, but yeah I saw you sent a notice about that too, so

3:42:54: Tony: Yeah, so I wanted to own that right away and just say, I slipped, it was my birthday yesterday, I had a lot on my mind, but, I missed it, it was my own fault.

3:43:03: Mchale: Could you move the microphone over a bit more

3:43:06: Tony: How bout this. (Mchale – yeah thank you)

3:43:07: Frank: Can you hear us ok sir?

3:43:08: Yeah, I got you now. So as to a sober birthdate, what are you, what do you have as yours?

3:43:12: Tony: 6/26/24 was my last use. Or, 6/25, so my first full sober day was 6/26/24.

3:43:21: Mchale: Ok, and then there were the positive xylazines before that you contest all of those is that right?

3:43:26: Tony: Yeah, I strongly don't believe I ever had it in my system, nor did I use intentionally.

3:43:33: Mchale: And you understand that in this program, that it's not necessarily intentional use, its whether it's in your system.

3:43:40: Tony: I just, I doubt the veracity of the testing regime. I really, I – Your Honor, to the best of my ability to tell the truth, I don't think it passed through my body.

3:43:50: Frank: Intentionally, or unintentionally Your Honor, I think is what my client was intending to say.

3:43:56: Tony: Yeah, I just, I am nowhere near drug use or drug users.

3:44:01: Mchale: The report, the daily status report coming out today, there's a lot in it, I've been through that, went through it last week when we were here, before Frank took over as your attorney, and then when I get to the recommendation part of it, it says, that additionally Tony appears unwilling or unable to follow drug court program expectations and/or requirements and the recommendation is that you be put on an excluded period just in general, and that the state is requesting termination of your participation in the program. , so, the first part of that, what do you make of, ah, the, , reported appearance of being unable or unwilling to comply, or , comply with the expectations and/or requirements.

3:45:00: Tony: Well, (to Frank- I think it's me first) I, I think that, , that there's a nuanced truth there which is that I'm completely willing to comply with the policies. I do more than my sober supports, I finished my community service, I finished MRT. Even if I'm unhappy with some aspect of the program or I've been vocal about it, I still see it as my duty to uphold the actions required by the court. And I'm still doing that as of today, like, I missed a UA yesterday, man. I feel terrible, like I'm, I'm wrecked that that happened. And like, I don't think that I've been unwilling to comply with any part, I've just been vocal about my belief about the testing regime. I've done that actions that the court requires – I've done perfectly except for my missed UA yesterday.

3:45:52: Mchale: What about with the housing issues there? I mean how-

3:45:56: Tony: I mean, well, I'm a little unsure- is it a third party vendor that's not related to my compliance, or is it part of drug court?

3:46:05: Mchale: It's part of, I mean, you're fortunate in being part of drug court that we're able to provide housing and you're expected to comply with the rules of housing. The housing, what the program itself is a gift. The housing is, as I see it is a bonus gift. And it's a gift for, sadly not just for people in our drug court program, but for other people that may have, may be coming from having been in jail or in prison, that have substance use issues, or may have had substance issues in the past and so in living in those situations it's a community that really needs to be, respected and maintained in a sober way, and so there are strict rules that are set up for everybody that's in the housing and so that is something that's super important is to comply with the housing directive, and as part of that housing, it comes through us. Unlike a lot of places around the country or even in our area, when one is in housing and a UA comes up positive or there is a violation of the rule people are immediately out, and here we've got the benefit of what's called a housing stabilization

plan. And that's something that's something that's worked on through our program and I haven't seen that you're willing to cooperate with the housing stabilization plan.

3:47:43: Frank: Your Honor, may I speak? Excuse me, Tony.

3:47:43 Mchale: Well I want to hear from Tony, I'll get to you in just a second.

3:47:50: Tony: So, I've had three xylazine false positives, in my opinion, two of which I completed housing stabilization plan for. Nobody has asked me to do a housing stabilization plan for the most recent one, I think because it hasn't been sanctioned yet. And I'm completely willing to do that too. And further, I followed all of the housing policies too. So, I'm wildly compliant with rules, actually. That's, that's – yeah, nobody's asked me to do a third one, and I think that that comes after the sanction, but I did the other two with no problem. And, and, further, each housing stabilization plan comes with action items for me, I completed the action items and updated case management as I did each of those, so not only did I do the meetings, I completed all the action items for all the housing stabilization plans I've done as well.

3:48:45: Mchale: ...I'll ...

23:48:56: Frank: Your Honor, I have copies of those first two housing stabilization plans in my hand right here, I'd be happy to pass those forward your Honor, but, my understanding with talking with other participants in the drug court program, that, there is essentially a situation here where the housing stabilization plan as it relates to the April 9th 2025 xylazine is a bit premature because the sanction hasn't been adjudicated yet. And for the record we intend to contest that particular xylazine positive, we feel that, through our efforts to bring the matter to the courts and have it fully vetted out that, we'll be able to show that the standalone xylazine positive is not reliable. And, so, that might be a bit of a – getting ahead of myself, but it is one of the things that I want to make sure because we are here to discuss that April 9th positive, it's our contention that it's a false positive.

3:50:03: McHale: Ok, alright. I've got that, I understand that y'all wanna contest it and what's your process for planning to contest that?

3:50:09: Frank: , I'm in the process right now of trying to locate a toxicologist, that will be able to come in, with sufficient credentials to be designated as an expert, to be able to attest to the, the veracity of xylazine being in the system as a standalone, even in the more highly sensitive confirmatory tests, that was applied here. And so that's, that's the intention, obviously that will take some time, I note that the public defender's office has been given, you know considerable leeway to develop that themselves. We would want the same sort of leeway as we move forward, and I would be here to update the court accordingly regarding my efforts, I understand that this, obviously is contingent on the

motion to terminate and whether or not that is adjudicated either in favor of the state or in favor of Mr. Jones, , but that is our intention, should Mr. Jones be permitted to continue in the program. On the motion to terminate, I do have some issue, with the pattern and practice of the drug court to apply an exclusion, prior to that motion being adjudicated. And the same, for applying an excluded status when a sanction is, or when, a UA is being contested. And the reason for that is that it actually results in a deprivation of Right. And I note that this is not a contested issue because, Ms. Mason addresses this in her recommendation hearing note where she ties the excluded period to the removal from housing. And, for that reason, if there is going to be an excluded period that's considered prior to a motion to terminate, I would respectfully request an opportunity to brief the court. I think the state has a duty to show where that is a policy within its manual. I've looked through the manual now, I've looked at the section on excluded periods, I'll read that to the record, 'If you experience temporary medical or other issues including travel that impacts your ability to attend treatment sessions take UAs or meet other drug court requirements, the court may place you on a temporary excluded period. Time during the excluded period will not count towards the consecutive days of compliance needed to promote to the next phase or complete the DDC program.' It says nothing in there about that being a penalization, or even an interim step, during a contested proceeding. The same holds true on the section for termination, which is on page 16 of the handbook, and it says there that there may be instances when continuation in the program is unproductive for you, it gives reasons as to why it would be unproductive. It indicates that termination may be voluntary or involuntary, and it goes into further detail about what an involuntary termination means. It does nothing, within that contract, to indicate that a preemptive exclusion period should apply. And when that excluded status results in the deprivation of a private right, I think there are some serious concerns that are raised. And, as Ms. Mason stated, the net effect of this excluded period being applied now, pre-any, prior to any adjudication on the motion to terminate, is that Mr. Jones is gonna be kicked out of his housing. Mr. Jones is also protected under the ADA, he has PTSD, it's documented, the court's aware of that. And to apply that now without having this fully vetted, I think would be a mistake. The reality is that many of the communications, albeit not the process or procedure I would've pursued, had I been representing Mr. Jones at the time, but, many of the communications to the court and to other parties were zealous advocacy by Mr. Jones on his own behalf. He was in a pro se status. He had tried to raise these issues to his previous counsel, Byron – Davis I believe is it? (Tony – Gale) Gale? Byron Gale. Ah, he tried to raise these issues with Byron Gale but he was met with, essentially, no help whatsoever. Arguably an ineffective assistance of counsel. Which I find intriguing now because the same public defense office is actually taking the stand to question and to push back against these standalone xylazine testing regime. Or testing positives. and so ya know, had

that happened when Mr. Jones was first experiencing these positive tests, I think we'd be in a very different situation, but Mr. Jones felt, I would argue rightfully so, that he had to rely on himself versus the counsel that was appointed to him, in order to try and advocate for himself. Now, what I will tell you is I'm not going anywhere. I understand, you know, that some people are of the mindset that you can't un-ring a bell, but I, I tend to disagree. I think that with my involvement we could actually inject some , order and formality to these issues but what I will say is, you know, Mr. Jones does deserve to have a voice. And that hasn't been accomplished through his efforts, I think, frankly, because he doesn't understand civil procedure. But, that voice and those issues are meritorious. They're deserving of this court's attention, so that this court can continue to be a, ah, an objective adjudicator and overseer of this program. At the end of the day I understand that this is a therapeutic system. It's a collaborative system. But where we are right now is very much adversarial, and we should not lose sight of that.

3:56:19: Mchale: Well, part of it, I feel like we're- it is collaborative. I mean there there, case after case talks about the unusual nature of drug court being a collaborative process. And and that, a big part of that, is, it's not just the lawyers, the judge, the program that are collaborative, but it's got to be the participant that's been collaborative. And so, issues that you know, people have to be held accountable. And when one is caught out with a UA or with ah, that's positive, or with some other issue – mind you I get that y'all want to challenge the xylazine UA, but other issues, it – it doesn't look as it feel, Tony, as if you've been necessarily collaborative at all in that sense, and the, its almost threatening in some ways when someone's contacted you about it, about, here's a notice of claim, here's a draft of my section 1983 complaint, then reporting, say with housing, , to, , (Kristine – to the IRS), yeah housing issues that are there, so that – the collaborative part is what I have a problem with. So what's-

3:57:46: Frank: On the issue of housing I think it's important to recognize something, at the front end of this, when Mr. Jones was going into this program, he then had an opportunity to house with a family member, and the staff at- (Mchale: He did or did not?) – he did. He did have an opportunity that came up after he initially engaged, and he was pushed into going into that housing, pushed and said it was required that he goes into the Weld housing. You know, he had an opportunity to be in an environment that would have actually not attributed to further PTSD, that would have also been a stable house for him. And so there's that aspect of it that I don't know if the courts aware or not. Like you know he did try to push for that and was rejected. And was told he had to stay in the Weld housing. And so, you know as far as Weld housing it's one of those things where on one end it seems to me like housing is a requirement of this program based on me getting up to speed, and it seems like Weld is in effect acting as a gatekeeper, towards that service, and I would say that in

reviewing some of the communications between Mr. Bardacke and Mr. Jones that there has almost been a bullying nature from Mr. Bardacke, and a threatening nature from Mr. Bardacke as to Mr. Jones. He has threatened housing, ongoing housing, as essentially a consequence if Mr. Jones, ya know, continues to ask questions, continues to advocate for himself. And I think that should disturb the court and it certainly disturbed my client and it essentially exacerbated his PTSD, which is documented, I mean he is on disability now as we speak. Yes please go ahead. Tony would like to say something.

4:00:00: Tony: Your Honor may I speak to that?

4:00:01: Mchale: Yeah, briefly, go ahead.

4:00:02: Tony: Yeah, so you know, on the day of my 4/15 hearing, I just briefly mentioned it but I want to tell you what happened that day, is, the day before I asked Katie for a contract, for a copy of the contract I signed. That's it. I said – actually it was two days before, I said- I know it's a Sunday. Don't respond until tomorrow if you're not working. Could you send me a copy of the contract? She sent it and she was like, the director wants to meet with you. And so I was like ok cool. And so, a couple hours before that hearing, he came to the house and I was like, I said, I said hey, I want to start off by saying thank you for the housing, I like my house manager Rick, I feel like he is a gift in my life. And he was like, 'you're gonna stop talking about your court stuff in this house, or you're gonna find yourself homeless real quick. And I was like, we're all in court together. How could I not talk about court with people in this house? And he's like, I'll change the rules, I make the rules. And I was like, if you change the rules I'll follow those. Have I broken any? And he said, yeah you know when we tell people to leave we tell them you've got thirty minutes to get the fuck out. And I was like, 'do you what you gotta do, bro.' That's your housing vendor. So, after that yes, I looked at, are there legal angles that I can try to protect myself from. I know that if I become a whistleblower, maybe I have some more protections from becoming homeless in thirty minutes. Right? My PTSD is from when I was homeless, man, I'm terrified of that. Your housing vendor said that to me in the living room.

4:01:40: Frank: And I'd also like to point out on information and belief-

4:01:43: Mchale: Briefly I gotta give..

4:01:45: Frank: Oh, understood, Your Honor. Sorry to interrupt you.

4:01:49: Kristine: Yeah, I just wanna just get into some of these things that are being said. I think that was represented that Tony was forced into housing during the process of the waiver and agreement. There is a discussion during the waiver and agreement that says you, or the ah, transfer into housing, not the waiver and agreement. In the transfer into drug court. Because Tony was transferred in, he was not direct filed. He came into drug court at

his request, the state actually waived hipro designation to bring tony into drug court. And during that process of the transfer and transfer agreement, it is actually talked about how you will either have drug court housing or drug court approved housing, sober housing. Let me go over that. I want to bring up at the notes from Nov 4th 2024, from Katie, entered into Monitor, it says verbatim “Anthony (Tony) attended housing portion of O&I today, reported he is currently staying in a tent. Reported he’s in urgent housing crisis. It’s getting cold, really need housing, and wants to be placed on DC housing wait list at this time. Tony was informed during presentation that a negative UA is needed before moving a participant into housing. Tony was directed to talk to DC housing case manager and talk about shelter and next steps to move tony into DC housing.” So the idea Tony is told he is required to live in DC housing is not consistent with drug court rules or procedures here.

4:03:17: Kristine: And I want to get back to the point here, this is not just about housing, this is not just about one particular email, we are talking about a pattern of behavior. We’re asking this set for termination -the state will be asking for termination, we’re asking to set for a hearing and place on excluded because, as we discussed during staffing, Mr. Jones has made himself needs exceeds as a result of his approach and his posturing whenever he’s confronted with any attempt to discuss compliance issues, following drug court established procedures or address accountability issues. And it’s the level of discourse, and the conflict, and the immediate result, or immediate emails that result in all the case managers but our program manager having been unable to work with Mr. Jones prior to April 23rd of this year. On April 23rd is when Ms. Mason emailed Mr. Jones with an attempt to address the most recent positive UA, and that response, okay, that is not a response that he came up with later, it’s not a response down the road, the response that Mr. Jones has was to send a draft of a legal filing and demand that the program change the way that it handles UA testing, and I think that this is the pattern here that this developed over time, Mr. Jones, whenever he is contacted with any sort of issue of accountability to something that he doesn’t agree with, meets that part with a promise that they will either be named either in the filing or have their licensing attacked, and does not respond to the underlying issue of compliance, and does not respond to the underlying issues regarding the program. So, Mr. Jones in transferring to drug court, he had those agreements, you know the waiver

and agreement, policies and procedures, you know, he came into drug court under the understanding that *this* (emphasis added) is the program he is to follow, *this* (emphasis added) drug court--as it is today--is the way that he is supposed to follow it. He agreed to abide by those. He agreed for your honor to follow the policies and procedures and have those UAs be a basis for his sanction at a future date. Tony agreed to two sanctions for those prior UAs. So we are – those have already been adjudicated. I know he wants to re-open that door and re-adjudicate those. But, you know, here in drug court we are directed by statute to follow best practices. And participants are to be subject to the best practice - to the rules of the program according to best practices. What Tony is asking today is that the court set aside the rules for Tony. That we set aside the rules and procedures regarding housing, regarding UAs, and regarding the process of this, to allow him to continue. But that would be inequitable for everyone else in the program and it also wouldn't be consistent with our program, with drug court. So the state is just not in support of allowing Tony to continue at this point. It is his behavior and his actions which made him needs exceeds by resulting in having nobody else to work with in our program, which is...a large issue to say because I know that there have been a lot of instances on individuals, that people will have a blow up, but the ongoing relentlessness of the emails, the ongoing relentlessness of the argument and confrontation is why he is needs exceeds. It's not a particular argmuent, its not a particular belief, it's the relentlessness of being confronted with his emails once accountability is demanded.

4:06:40: Frank: So if I could just rebut or respond to those characterizations, first as it relates to Ms. Mason and the dispute as it relates to her communication, we dispute that having the inclusion of details of his alleged positive testing in an email that also cc'd the housing vendor was an appropriate use of the release of information waiver that was signed. If you look to the terms of that we can discuss that but I don't want to get lost in the weeds, I do want to address the fact that there is a unique situation here in Mr. Jones' communication because at the time he was pro se. He has the right to zealously advocate for himself in that sense he puts on the hat as his own attorney. And any attorney would be able to zealously advocate on behalf of their client without his without that client then being subject to some sort of punishment. The reality is the issue of standalone xylazine testing has not been adjudicated before this court. There are numerous, now numerous people that have objected and are now contesting those. In fact there's one individual that I met out in the hallway that took a UA for another jurisdiction that tested negative for xylazine but then took one-

4:08:09 Mchale: Yeah I don't want to get into other people's cases

4:08:10: Frank: But it's important. What I'm saying your Honor is if in fact these positives have been falsely attributed to Mr. Jones, Mr. Jones is right to express frustration in that process. This is not a decision he made lightly, the decision to go pro se, on his own, was out of frustration for not feeling like he was being advocated for at all. And then what did he do? He advocated for himself. Now certainly, again, I don't agree with the approach, but that is the hat he was wearing at the time. What I can say is that those aren't communications that – anything related to the legal analysis pertaining to Mr. Jones' participation in this program is not going to be going through Mr. Jones, it is going to be going through me. But he does deserve to have a voice. There are – if your Honor can look – because it sounds like you've read the emails. It sounds like you've read-

4:09:16: Mchale: I got them too

4:09:17: Frank: I hear you your Honor, but what I'm saying is, unless you can say there are not issues, that no issue in there is worth further consideration by this court, then we do need to have some motion practice, we do need to have some briefing on these issues. And as to the issue of exclusion prior to adjudication on a motion to terminate, that is, as I mentioned in staffing, the proverbial cart before the horse. You are effectively exercising a sanction, the net effect as admitted by the state, would be to remove him from housing prior to a motion to terminate being adjudicated. And while that may be the practice of this court, it's not in the handbook, and it's certainly not something that makes any sense when you consider the private interest that is being removed from Mr. Jones, which is specific – his housing. And the effect that is going to have on him, as an American with disability due to his PTSD. Certainly, if the motion to terminate is found in favor of the state, then that makes sense, but to apply that sanction now before that motion is even been briefed or argued or decided by you your honor is premature. Especially given the net effect that we're dealing with here.

4:10:42: Kristine: If I may briefly respond to the housing (Mchale- Ya, go ahead). Alright, so on the policies and procedures manual, which is available on the website, on page 3 (To Frank- it's not the handbook it's the policies and procedures manual), on #7 it states DDC Services it states drug court services provides services for drug court participants including program orientation and referrals to treatment housing etc, right. And, it specifically says DDC Participants. If you scroll downwards onto page 4, number 10 states DDC Participants are those eligible defendants who are referred to drug court. DDC participants are expected to adhere to the courts orders and directives, and to follow DDC rules and requirements and attend all scheduled (Mchale – slow down, slow down, you get going fast). Sorry. To follow DDC rules and requirements and attend all scheduled and required meetings including DDC hearings. So participants who are active in the program are eligible

to get services. If you are not eligible in the program you are no longer considered an active participant and should not be getting services and resources through the program. I think that asking housing to keep open positions for people who are pending termination when we know that termination can take weeks, sometimes months, depending sometimes on what other cases are happening, is not consistent with the court's rules or with the court's practices or with the policies and procedures manual, with those definitions discussing DDC services or contracted agencies.

4:12:16: Frank: I actually agree her. I agree with that policy 100%. The problem with what she read there though, is there has not been a determination of ineligibility at this point. And so therefore to suggest that the housing is removed because he is ineligible, put onto an excluded status, is actually inappropriate. It frankly, could be subject to further appeal should a decision like that be made, in light of the fact that he is still, until that motion has been decided, an eligible participant within this program. So that is the crux of it. We have no issue with adjudicating and with briefing the motion for termination, and in fact if you are inclined to do an exclusion prior to that motion for termination being adjudicated, we would respectfully request formal briefing as to applying this excluded status prior to that motion for termination being adjudicated. We have a right to preserve the record, to create a record as it relates to the underlying case precedent that applies when the net effect of this is to deprive Mr. Jones of a private interest – of his housing. And so if the court is inclined to look at doing an excluded status prior to the motion for termination, we would request to brief that, we could do it pretty quickly. But to do it ad hoc on the fly like this, it deprives Mr. Jones of being able to establish a record for himself for future reference if and as is needed.

4:14:03: Mchale: I'll say, from the handbook, everybody relies on the handbook, if you go to page 2, it says the handbook for king county adult diversion drug court is designed to structure but not to eliminate decision making for all those individuals who seek to join the program as well as those who participate in it. The court reserves the right in each individual case to make discretionary decisions consistent with the law and public policies. So while its structure, its not the law. I so strongly believe in this program. You know that I believe in this program. I think sometimes I go too far in trying to keep people in the program. I do that because I see the opportunities that come with people who are successful in this program and I can go back to the Sykes case that I talked about before, and it talks about why we have this program. Because before there was a drug court program it wasn't working to just send people off to prison to deal with the drug issues that they've had and it was a chance to try something different, and to try something different in a collaborative way, its designed to be collaborative. The case that addresses that directly is State v Starkgraf, 29 Washington App 30 from 2023.

4:15:41: Tony: Yeah, Starkgraf got terminated due to, he tried to contest his based on he had first amendment infringement based on social network postings, but they found other compliance issues.

4:15:54: Mchale: Right, that's true, so-

4:15:54: Tony: And Sykes also held up that due process-

4:15:55: Mchale: Let me finish, Tony, y'all had your shot at this. It takes collaboration, and that's just not what I've seen from you. You've done things on your own, but the way its been presented from you is that you can't really be held accountable. To the extent that we, case management has not been able to work with you. In fact, Christina, who I think is still in here, Ms. Mason, took over as the case manager in your case and then in response to the positive xylazine from the 9th, initially you submitted a multi-page section 1983 complaint listing her and nine other people as potential defendants in that. And then further, beyond that, about a week later, my understanding is that there was a complaint that was initiated with the Washington state DOH about her licensed independent clinical social worker status. You make it such that people aren't able to work directly with you. If they're confronting you with something that should be collaboratively addressed, its addressed in a threatening or harassing way. Similarly and probably more concerning was an email you sent at one point to Mr. Bardacke at Weld Housing, and you know you've had complaints there, allegations that your civil rights were violated in different ways, beyond addressing those specifically, the letter indicated that you submitted complaint, you also submitted complaints to the US Dept of Housing and Urban Development, the Seattle Office for Civil Rights, The King County Department of Human Services, The Washington State Human Rights Commission, The Seattle Dept of Construction and Inspection, Washington State Longterm Care Ombudsman, The IRS, The Washington Attorney General Civil Rights Division, The Better Business Bureau. The most concerning part of that letter though, is then at the end, the final paragraph, it says, or it reads, given the breadth of the documented concerns, and the number of independent agencies now reviewing Weld's practices, you may wish to consider recommending to Weld Seattle's BOD that you step aside from your current leadership position. Such a recommendation can help limit ongoing institutional exposure and demonstrate proactive corrective action in response to serious governance risks. To me that appears threatening as does the interaction with Ms. Mason.

4:19:34: Frank: Your Honor, did you have a chance-

4:19:35: Mchale: Please, let me (Frank: Thank you your honor). So, where I am with this with you in the program is, the program can't manage you. We're in a situation in which its

unable to work with you in any sense. I mean it would be, you know if, Frank is representing you, and Frank – you told Frank you were gonna file a legal malpractice action against him, that would put him in a rather difficult situation in which he wouldn't be able to work with you. I mean, I see it like that in some ways, so I'm in a position where I don't see, and the state is moving to terminate your participation in the program so we'll see where that goes, we'll have to set a hearing for that, but until then I am gonna grant the request or recommendation that you um-

4:20:57: Frank: Your honor, are you gonna do that without any opportunity to brief that issue?

4:21:03: Mchale: That's all I can do today. I can't – if I've got no way that the program can manage him, I just, its where I am, so I'm gonna have to put you on an excluded period in general. And as to briefing if y'all can work on a briefing schedule, you know we can. And the other thing you still have your motion to dismiss, I would be willing to consider that before the, set date for the termination hearing.

4:21:34: Frank: I think at this point since you're making this a formal order, I think I'll be filing a motion for reconsideration, and I'll be presenting the legal analysis through that mechanism for the court to consider further its decision. As it stands right now, this decision is made without the opportunity for Mr. Jones to be heard as to the underlying case law that governs this kind of decision, and in my opinion its being done prematurely, because there's not been an adjudication that he's terminated from the program as of yet.

4:22:16: Mchale: I note that, that's what we're gonna work on, I don't know if y'all have talked about dates or briefing schedule, if you're gonna file a motion for reconsideration that may change the briefing schedule I'll work on, but you know you gotta get that within that time period.